

MULTISET SPACES IN AN INFINITE GROUPS

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ABSTRACT: In this article, we investigate the idea of multi set and multi set spaces in infinite group theory based on Nazmul paper. Also, we analyze the concept of multigroups to permit flexibility of the identity element from a group, multicose, multi normal subgroup and proved some related results.

Keywords: *Multiset, Multigroup, Coset, Normal subgroup, infinigroup, Multiset spaces, Min and Max operators.*

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1: INTRODUCTION: The theory fuzzy set was first introduced by Zadeh in 1965. Since inception it has evoked a lot of research. For more details can be found in ([3][4][10]). The theory of multisets is an extension of the set theory. Theoretic study has included algebra aspect of fuzzy set and multiset. Mordeson[6] and Bhutani [5] collaborated with Rosenfiel, the initiation of theory of groups in order to establish the algebraic structure of fuzzy sets, and worked extensively on this subject with some new results described in [6]. Onasanya [8] critically studied the notion and carried out some thorough reviews in fuzzy groups and anti-fuzzy groups. In [7], the underlying structure in group theory was replaced with multisets and some fundamental properties were presented. Moreover, as a suitable generalization of classical group theory, Awolola and Ibrahim Awulola and Ejegwa [[1],[2]] discussed the concept. Further and investigated their related properties. In this paper, we investigate the idea of multi set and multi set spaces in infinite group theory based on Nazmul paper. Also, we analyze the concept of multigroups to permit flexibility of the identity element from a group, multicose, multi normal subgroup and proved some related results.

SECTION-2: PRELIMINARIES AND VARIOUS BASIC CONCEPTS

Definition-2.1 Let X be a set A multiset (MS) drawn from X is represented by a count function C_M defined as $C_M: X \rightarrow Z_0^+$ where $X = \{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$.

For each $x \in X$, $C_M(x)$ denotes the number of occurrences of the element x in the multiset M the representation of the multiset M drawn from $X = \{x_1, x_2, x_3 \dots x_n\}$ will be as $M = \{x_1, x_2, x_3 \dots x_n\}_{m_1, m_2, m_2 \dots mn}$ such that x_j appears m times ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n$) in M .

Let, for any positive integer p , $[X]^p$ be the set of multisets drawn from X such that no element in the multiset occurs more than ' p ' times and $[X]^\infty$ be the set of all multisets drawn from X such that there is no limit on the number of occurrences of a objects in an multiset. Therefore $[X]^p$ and $[X]^\infty$ are reference to multiset spaces.

Definiton-2.2 Let $M_1, M_2, M_j \in [X]^p, j \in J$ then,

- (i) $M_1 = M_2$ if and only if $C_{M_1(x)} = C_{M_2(x)} \forall x \in X$.
- (ii) $\cap_{j=1} M_j = \min_{j \in J} C_{M_j(x)}, \forall x \in X$.
- (iii) $\cup_{j=1} M_j = \max_{j \in J} C_{M_j(x)}, \forall x \in X$.
- (iv) $\cup_{j=1} M_j = \max_{j \in J} C_{M_j(x)}, \forall x \in X$.
- (v) $M_j^c = p - C_{M_j(x)}, \forall x \in X, p \in Z^{-1}$.

Definition-2.3 Let X be a group. A harmonized multiset ' A ' over X is called harmonized multi group if the count function of the element of ' A ' or $C_A(x)$ satisfies the following conditions:

- (i) $C_A^n(x * y) \geq \min\{C_A^n(x), C_A^n(y)\}$
- (ii) $C_A^n(x^{-1}) = C_A^n(x), \forall x \in X$.

Example-2.4 Let $D = \langle s_1/s_1^2 \rangle \times \langle s_2/s_2^2 = 1 \rangle X \dots$ be an infinite elementary abelian group.

Let $\mu \in MG(D)^\alpha$ an harmonized multi group. Then in fact $\mu \in MG(D)^{\mu(1)}$. So ' μ ' is constant on some infinite $F \subseteq D$. On the other hand, setting $D_0 = \emptyset, D_j = \langle s_1 \rangle X \dots X \langle s_j \rangle, \mu(s) = j + 1$ provided $S \in D_{j+1}/D_j$ then $\mu \in MG(D)^\alpha$ is harmonized multi group with $\mu \notin MG(D)^\alpha$ for any positive integer K . Hence harmonized multigroups may provide new tools in infinite group theory.

Definition- 2.5 Let $A, B \in [X]^p$, we have the following the definitions;

- (i) $C_{A \circ B}^n(x) = \max\{\text{Min}\{C_A^n(y), C_A^n(z)\} / y, z \in X, yz = x\}$
- (ii) $C_{A^{-1}}^n(x) = C_A^n(x^{-1})$

we call $A \circ B$ the product of A and B and A^{-1} the inverse of A .

Definition-2.6 Let $A, B \in M_G(x)$. Then A is said to be a harmonized multi group of B if $B \subseteq A$.

Example: Let $X = \{a, b/a^2 = b^2 = 1, ba = ab\}$, where

$$A = \{1, a, b, ab\}_{2,3,1,1} \text{ and } B = \{1, a, b, ab\}_{1,2,4,4} \cdot \cdot$$

Clearly, $A, B \in M_{G(x)}$ and $B \subseteq A$. Thus, B is harmonized sub multigroup of A.

Definition-2.7 Let $A \in M_{G(x)}$. Then ‘A’ is called an abelian harmonized multigroup over X if

$$C_A^n(x * y) = C_A^n(y * x), \text{ for all } x, y \in X. \text{ The set of all abelian harmonized multigroup over X is denote by } AM_{G(x)}.$$

SECTION-3: MAIN RESULTS

Proposition-3.1 Let $A \in M_G(x)$. Then we have the following

- (i) $C_A^n(x^p) \geq C_A^n(x), \forall x \in X$.
- (ii) If $C_A^n(x^{-1}) \leq C_A^n(x)$, then $C_A^n(x^{-1}) = C_A^n(x)$.
- (iii) If $C_A^n(x) \leq C_A^n(y)$, for some $x, y \in X$, then $C_A^n(xy) = C_A^n(yx)$.
- (iv) $C_A^n(xy^{-1}) = C_A^n(e)$ implies $C_A^n(x) = C_A^n(y)$.

Proof: (i) and (ii) follows immediately

(iii) Let $C_A^n(x) > C_A^n(y)$ for some $, y \in X$. Since $A \in M_G(x)$, then

$$C_A^n(x) \geq \min\{C_A^n(x), C_A^n(y)\} = C_A^n(x).$$

Now, $C_A^n(x) = C_A^n(yxy^{-1}) \geq \min\{C_A^n(yx), C_A^n(y)\} = C_A^n(yx)$.

Since, $C_A^n(x) > C_A^n(y)$ and $C_A^n(x) > C_A^n(xy)$.

Therefore $C_A^n(xy) = C_A^n(y)$, the equality $> C_A^n(yx) = C_A^n(x)$ can be obtained similarly.

(iii) Given $A \in M_{G(x)}$ and $C_A^n(xy^{-1}) = C_A^n(e)$ for all $x, y \in X$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} C_A^n(x) &= C_A^n(x(y^{-1})y) = C_A^n((xy^{-1})y) \leq \min\{C_A^n(xy^{-1}), C_A^n(y)\} \\ &= \max\{C_A^n(e), C_A^n(y)\} = C_A^n(y). \end{aligned}$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} C_A^n(y) &= C_A^n(y^{-1}) \\ &= C_A^n(e * y^{-1}) \\ &= C_A^n((x^{-1}x)y^{-1}) \\ &= \min\{C_A^n(x^{-1}), C_A^n(xy^{-1})\} \\ &= \min\{C_A^n(x), C_A^n(e)\} \\ &= C_A^n(x) \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $C_A^n(x) = C_A^n(y)$.

Proposition-3.2: Let $A \in [x]^p$. Then $A \in M_G(x)$ if and only if $C_A^n(xy^{-1}) \geq \min\{C_A^n(x), C_A^n(y)\}$

holds for all $x, y \in X$.

Proof : Let $A \in M_G(x)$. Then $C_A^n(xy^{-1}) \geq \min\{C_A^n(x), C_A^n(y^{-1})\}$

$$\geq \min\{C_A^n(x), C_A^n(y^{-1})\} \quad \forall x, y \in X.$$

Conversely, let the given condition be satisfied,

$$C_A^n(xy^{-1}) \geq \min\{C_A^n(x), C_A^n(y)\}$$

Now, $C_A^n(e) = C_A^n(x * x^{-1})$
 $\geq \min\{C_A^n(x), C_A^n(x)\}$
 $= C_A^n(x)$

and

$$C_A^n(x^{-1}) = C_A^n(ex^{-1}) \geq \min\{C_A^n(e), C_A^n(x)\}$$

$$= C_A^n(x).$$

Hence, $C_A^n(xy) = C_A^n((x(y^{-1})^{-1}) \geq \min\{C_A^n(x), C_A^n(y^{-1})\} = \min\{C_A^n(x), C_A^n(y)\}$.

Proposition-3.3: Let $A \in [x]^p$. Then $A \in M_G(x)$ if and only if $A \geq A \circ A$ and $A^{-1} = A$.

Proof: Let $x, y \in X$. Since $A \in M_G(x)$. Then

$$C_A^n(x * y) \geq \min\{C_A^n(x), C_A^n(y)\}$$

Hence $C_{A \cup A}(Z) = \max\{\min\{C_A^n(x), C_A^n(y)\}\}$
 $\leq \max_{z=x*y} C_A^n(x * y)$
 $= C_A^n(z)$

Therefore, $A \geq A \circ A$.

On the other hand, $A \in M_G(x)$ thus, $C_A^n(x^{-1}) = C_A^n(x), \forall x \in X$

But by definition, $C_A^n(x^{-1}) = C_A^n(x)$,

Therefore, $A^{-1} = A$.

Conversely, let the given condition be satisfied. If $A = A \circ A$ and $A^{-1} = A$. Then it sufficient to prove $A \in M_G(x)$.

Now,

$$C_{A \circ A}^n(x) = \max_{z=xy} \{\min\{C_A^n(x), C_A^n(y)\}\}$$

$$\geq \min\{C_A^n(x), C_A^n(y)\}, \forall x, y \in X$$

Hence, $C_A^n(x * y) \geq \min\{C_A^n(x), C_A^n(y)\}, xy = z$.

Since the equation $C_A^n(x) = C_A^n(x)$ and $C_{A^{-1}}^n(x) = C_A^n(x), \forall x \in X$.

Therefore $A \in M_G(x)$.

Proposition -3.4 The union of two harmonized multigroup also harmonized multigroup.

Proof: Let A and B be two harmonized multigroup of X.

Let $x, y \in A \cup B$, implies $x, y \in A$ or $x, y \in B$.

Therefore, $C_A^n(x * y) \geq \min\{C_A^n(x), C_A^n(y)\}$ or $C_B^n(x * y) \geq \min\{C_B^n(x), C_B^n(y)\}$

Now,

$$C_{A \cup B}^n(xy) = \min\{C_A^n(xy), C_B^n(xy)\}$$

$$\geq \min\{\{\max\{C_A^n(x), C_A^n(y)\}, \max\{C_B^n(x), C_B^n(y)\}\}$$

$$= \min\{\max\{C_A^n(x), C_B^n(x)\}, \max\{C_A^n(y), C_B^n(y)\}\}$$

$$= \min\{C_{A \cup B}^n(x), C_{A \cup B}^n(y)\}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{and } C_{A \cup B}^n(x^{-1}) &= \min\{C_A^n(x^{-1}), C_B^n(x^{-1})\} \\ &= \min\{C_A^n(x), C_B^n(x)\} \\ &= C_{A \cup B}^n(x). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $A \cup B$ is also harmonized multigroup of X .

Remarks: If $\{A_j\}_{j \in I}$ is a family of a harmonized multigroups, then $\bigcap_{j \in I} A_j$ need not be a harmonized multigroup over X .

Remarks: If $A \in M_G(X)$, then A need not a harmonized multigroup of X , if and only if

$$C_A^n(x) = C_A^n(e), \forall x \in X.$$

Proposition-3.5 Let $A \in M_G(X)$ and $x \in X$. Then $C_A^n(x * y) = C_A^n(y) \forall y \in X$ if and only if $C_A^n(x) = C_A^n(e)$

Proof: If $C_A^n(xy) = C_A^n(y) \forall y \in X$, then $y = e$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Conversely, assume } C_A^n(x) = C_A^n(e) \text{ then } C_A^n(x * y) &\geq \min\{C_A^n(x), C_A^n(y)\} \\ &= C_A^n(y) \text{ and on the otherhand} \\ C_A^n(y) &= \min\{C_A^n(x^{-1}), C_A^n(xy)\} \\ &= C_A^n(xy). \end{aligned}$$

Proposition-3.6 Let $A \in M_G(X)$. Then the non-empty sets defined as

$$A^p = \{x \in X / C_A^n(x) \geq p, p \in z^+\}$$

and $A_* = \{x \in X / C_A^n(x) = C_A^n(e)\}$ are subgroups of X .

Proof: Let $x, y \in A^p$

It implies that $C_A^n(x) \geq p$ and $C_A^n(y) \geq p$. Then

$$C_A^n(x * y^{-1}) \geq \min\{C_A^n(x), C_A^n(y)\} \geq p \text{ and hence if } x, y \in A^p, \text{ then } xy^{-1} \in A^p.$$

Hence $A^p, p \in z^+$ are subgroups of X .

Again let $x, y \in A_*$

$$\text{Then } C_A^n(x) = C_A^n(y) = C_A^n(e)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now, } C_A^n(x * y^{-1}) &\geq \min\{C_A^n(x), C_A^n(y)\} \\ &= \min\{C_A^n(x), C_A^n(y)\} \\ &= C_A^n(e). \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{But } C_A^n(x * y) \geq C_A^n(xy^{-1})$$

$$C_A^n(xy^{-1}) = C_A^n(e)$$

Therefore $xy^{-1} \in A$

Hence A is a subgroup of X .

Proposition- 3.7 Let $A \in M_G(X)$. Then the following assertions are equivalent.

- (i) $C_A^n(xy) = C_A^n(yx), \forall x, y \in X$.
- (ii) $C_A^n(xyx^{-1}) = C_A^n(y), \forall x, y \in X$.

$$(iii) \quad C_A^n(xy x^{-1}) \geq C_A^n(y), \forall x, y \in X.$$

$$(iv) \quad C_A^n(xy x^{-1}) \leq C_A^n(y), \forall x, y \in X.$$

Proof: (i) \Rightarrow (ii) Let $x, y \in X$, then $C_A^n(x^{-1}xy) = C_A^n(ey) = C_A^n(y)$

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii) Trivial

$$(iii) \Rightarrow (iv) \quad C_A^n(xy x^{-1}) \leq C_A^n\{(x^{-1})(xy x^{-1})(x^{-1})^{-1}\} = C_A^n(y)$$

(iv) \Rightarrow (i) Let $x, y \in X$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} C_A^n(x * y) &= C_A^n(x[yx]x^{-1}) \\ &\geq C_A^n(xy) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Hence } C_A^n(xy) = C_A^n(yx)$$

Thus the above assertions are equivalent.

Proposition-3.8 Let $A \in AM_G(X)$. Then A_* , A^p , $p \in z^{-1}$ are normal subgroup of X .

Proof: (i) Assume $C_A^n(e) = 1$. Then $A = A^l$.

Hence it is not difficult to see that A_* is a normal subgroup of X .

(ii) Let $x \in X$ and $y \in A^p$. Then $C_A^n(y) \geq p$. Since $A \in AM_G(X)$, then

$$C_A^n(x * y) = C_A^n(y * x), \forall x, y \in X.$$

By proposition (3.7)

$$C_A^n(xy x^{-1}) = C_A^n(y) \text{ and this implies } C_A^n(xy x^{-1}) = C_A^n(y) \geq p.$$

Thus $xy x^{-1} \in A^p$ is a normal subgroup of X .

Conclusion: In this paper, we have defined different idea of multiset and multiset spaces in infinite group theory. we investigate the concept of multigroups to permit flexibility of the identity element. The vital role for the condition of multiset and multigroup to be multicose, multinormal subgroup are introduced.

Future work: The other researchers may obtain this result in the field of multisoft set and multi pythagorean fuzzy soft set.

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